

Index of genera mentioned in the notes on chorology (p. 5-98) and taxonomy and nomenclature (p. 99-173)

Note. – In order to make the information in the extensive notes on chorology (pages 5-98) and taxonomy and nomenclature (pages 99-173) in *Dumortiera* 122 more easily accessible, an index has been compiled of the genera mentioned in the text. If several species of a genus are commented on consecutively, the index refers only to the page where an introductory note on the genus as a whole or on the first species within the genus is mentioned. Synonyms mentioned in the notes on taxonomy and nomenclature are also included in the index.

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